

LEADERSHIP STRATEGY OF MADRASAH PRINCIPALS IN IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF MADRASAH ALIYAH TEACHERS IN PALANGKA RAYA AND PULANG PISAU, CENTRAL KALIMANTAN, INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study is motivated by the gap between the complex challenges faced by madrasahs in improving the quality of education and teacher performance and the need for effective leadership strategies. The purpose of this research is to describe and analyze the leadership strategies of madrasah principals in improving teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau, focusing on (1) madrasah management strategies; (2) madrasah program strategies; (3) madrasah resource support strategies; (4) madrasah institutional strategies; (5) obstacles; (6) solutions; and (7) teacher performance outcomes. Theories used include Kotten's leadership strategy, Richard and Steers' human performance blend, Maslow's performance motivation, and the teacher performance concepts from Permendiknas 16/2007 and P.M.A. 38/2018. This research employs a qualitative approach with descriptive-analytical methods involving data collection through documentation studies, interviews, observations, and data analysis using the Miles and Huberman model. The findings indicate that the two madrasah principals: (1) have clear and directed madrasah management strategies in line with Kotten's corporate strategy; (2) have clear and directed madrasah program strategies by Kotten's program strategy; (3) have optimal madrasah resource support strategies in line with Kotten's resource support strategy; (4) have effective madrasah institutional strategies in line with Kotten's institutional strategy; (5) face general and specific obstacles that need to be addressed appropriately according to Kotten's strategic obstacles; (6) have consolidation and expansion solutions that align with Hamphry's consolidation and expansion strategy; and (7) show an average improvement in teacher performance in line with the performance concepts of Richard and Steers, Maslow, Permendiknas 16/2007, and P.M.A. 38/2018. In conclusion, the leadership strategies of the two madrasah principals have successfully improved teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau, under the theories used and supported by the values of Pancasila, Sanusi's value system, and relevant policies. The researcher's discoveries and resulting products are valuable considerations for implementation.

Keywords: Leadership, Teacher Performance, Madrasah Strategy.

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a central and crucial role in shaping a competent and well-characterized generation (Mighwar 2022). Madrasah Aliyah (M.A.), an Islamic secondary education institution in Indonesia that emphasizes Islamic values and teachings, holds a strategic role and responsibility to provide quality education, both academically and morally (Adnan et al.,2022). In this context, the role of teachers in delivering effective and high-quality instruction is paramount (Sugiri, 2022).

The quality of teaching, learning and performance not only depends on the individual capabilities of teachers but is also greatly influenced by various factors, including the leadership strategies implemented by the Head of M.A. (Yohamintin et al. 2023). The Head of M.A. is a leader who guides, motivates, and directs teachers to achieve educational goals (Octavia 2020). Therefore, the leadership strategies employed by the Head of the Madrasah significantly impact teachers' performance at M.A., as they provide guidance, support, and inspiration for teachers to enhance the quality of teaching and learning (Afif et al. 2020).

The leadership strategies the Head of MA apply become key factors in improving teachers' performance (Ansori et al. 2022). Appropriate leadership strategies can provide the necessary guidance, motivation, and support for teachers to achieve optimal teaching standards (Argaeni, Wasliman, and Sulastini 2023). Conversely, ineffective or unsuitable leadership in the madrasah context can hinder teachers' development and negatively impact the quality of education provided (Enget 2020). However, in addressing the complexities of modern educational challenges, appropriate leadership strategies must be tailored to the specific characteristics and needs of the madrasah (Badrusalam 2021).

The significance of leadership strategies is underscored by theories such as Kotten (Rangkuti 2015), which states that educational leadership strategy is a plan, method, or far-sighted ability ('helicopter vision') employed by educational leaders to achieve specific goals for the advancement of educational institutions flexibly in overcoming unexpected challenges, including Madrasah Management Strategy (Corporate Strategy), Madrasah Program Strategy (Program Strategy), Madrasah Resource Support Strategy (Resource Support Strategy), and Madrasah Strategy (Institutional Strategy). The importance of performance is reinforced by theories from Richard and Steers (Yuriasari et al. 2024), which includes the ability to adapt, work performance job satisfaction, quality, and assessment from external parties. Apart from that, it is also reinforced by Maslow's theory of performance motivation or basic human needs, which refers to five levels of basic human needs that must be fulfilled before reaching higher levels: physiological needs, safety, love and belonging, esteem, and self-actualization (Al Mighwar et al. 2022). These theories and concepts will be the reference for this research.

Therefore, the Government of Indonesia has issued various policies to improve the performance of madrasah heads and MA teachers (Arbainsyah et al., n.d.). Law Number 14 of 2005 on Teachers and Lecturers (UU 14/2005), Government Regulation Number 74 of 2008 on Teachers (PP 74/2008), Government Regulation Number 28 of 2010 on Assignment of Teachers as School/Madrasah Heads (PP 28/2010), and Minister of Religious Affairs Regulation Number 58 of 2017 jo. PMA 24/2018 on Madrasah Heads, stipulates that the Head of MA must meet or even exceed the established performance standards, including personality, managerial, entrepreneurial, supervisory, and social competencies. UU 14/2005, Minister of National Education Regulation Number 16 of 2007 on Standards of Academic Qualifications and Teacher Competencies (Permendiknas 16/2007), and Minister of Religious Affairs Regulation Number 38 of 2018 on Continuous Professional Development for Teachers (PMA 38/2018) also stipulate that MA teachers must meet or even exceed the established performance

standards, including pedagogical, personality, social, and professional competencies. Furthermore, the Government, through the Ministry of Religious Affairs (Kemenag RI), has established mandatory performance assessment instruments, namely the Madrasah Head Performance Assessment (PKKM) regulated in the Director General of Education's Decree Number 111 of 2019 on Technical Guidelines for Madrasah Head Performance Assessment and the Teacher Performance Assessment (PKG), further regulated in Kepdirjenpendis 5581/2021 on Technical Guidelines for Competency Assessment of Madrasah Teachers and Educational Staff for 2021.

The Center for Educational Policy and Cultural Research of the Ministry of Education and Culture (Nurdin et al. 2023) states that despite the Government's high expectations, there are still empirical data that are quite concerning. School heads are often preoccupied with administrative and development matters, neglecting their primary educator duties. The preoccupation with administrative tasks causes them to be confused about prioritizing their primary duties, resulting in more time spent behind desks. Other activities usually performed by school heads include proposing additional learning spaces, participating in MGMP activities, attending head teacher meetings, and many other tasks. In such conditions, school heads with the burden of face-to-face teaching duties are feared to be less able to perform their tasks effectively (Center for Educational Policy and Cultural Research of the Ministry of Education and Culture).

This phenomenon also occurs at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN Kota Pulau Pisau. Preliminary studies by the researchers found that teachers at these two MAs are still differentiated based on status and rank, rather than on achievement and competence. The existence of several layers within the madrasah organization has shifted teaching from being a primary priority to merely pursuing social status. This condition is further exacerbated by differences in teachers' honorariums and a junior-senior system, making it very difficult to implement a high-quality system and culture. If this situation continues unchecked, both MAs will struggle to develop and will become less desirable institutions as their educational outcomes will not meet stakeholder expectations and regulatory demands. Changing this situation is certainly not easy, but the strong desire of the stakeholders of these two MAs to improve is the main capital that should be appreciated. Especially considering that MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya is a relatively advanced private madrasah aliyah, and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau is the only state madrasah aliyah in Palangka Raya City. Both MAs also experience an increase in student numbers with each new academic year.

Additionally, the two madrasahs focused on this research, namely MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, have different characteristics in terms of organizational culture, school policies, learning environments, and challenges faced. Therefore, it is important to understand how the leadership strategies employed by the Madrasah Heads in these institutions affect teachers' performance and their impact on education quality.

Previous research has explored issues of teacher performance and leadership in madrasahs but has not specifically focused on the leadership strategies of Madrasah Heads in improving teacher performance at the two madrasahs in this study. This ensures the originality and novelty

of this research and prevents duplication or plagiarism. Examples of relevant previous research include Khoiriyah's study (Zainur Rochim 2021) on strategic management at SMA N 1 Talun Blitar, Inayati's study (Huriaty, Esterani, and Saufi 2022) on the role of School Heads at two SMP Muhammadiyah schools, Hakim's study (Hakim, Amda, and Nuzuar 2018) on madrasah head management at MIN 04 Kepahiang, Munir's study (Munir 2011) on human resource development at MAN 3 Malang, Nuraida's (Nuraida 2013) study on teacher competence at Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Negeri Sei Agul Medan, Fahdini et al.'s study (Fahdini et al. 2014) on teacher competence in Sumedang Regency, and Ikbal's study (Ikbal 2018) study on teacher competence development management at MAN 1 Garut.

This research fills the gap by focusing on the leadership strategies of Madrasah Heads in improving teacher performance at the studied madrasahs. Meanwhile, there is a need for research on educational leadership and teachers in general education settings, as well as more focused research in the context of Madrasah Aliyah. Understanding the specific leadership strategies used by Madrasah Heads and their impact on the performance of Madrasah Aliyah teachers is crucial for the continuous improvement and development of Islamic education.

This research aims to describe and analyze the leadership strategies of madrasa heads in improving teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, with a focus on (1) madrasa management strategies; (2) madrasa program strategy; (3) madrasah resource support strategy; (4) madrasa strategy; (5) obstacles; (6) solution; and (7) teacher performance results.

Through a descriptive qualitative approach, this study aims to describe and analyze in-depth and comprehensively the leadership strategies used by the Madrasah Heads at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau. These institutions are chosen for their significance and representation of madrasah aliyah in the region. Qualitative research allows for a comprehensive exploration of the unique context, complexity, and nuances of leadership strategies and teacher effectiveness in the context of Islamic education. Through interviews, focus group discussions, classroom observations, and document analysis, this study aims to provide detailed and accurate insights into leadership practices and their impact on madrasah aliyah teachers.

Analyzing different leadership practices in these two madrasahs is expected to identify more effective strategies for overall teacher performance improvement. The results of this study are expected to provide practical guidance for madrasah heads and teachers in addressing current educational challenges and offer recommendations for madrasah administrators, policymakers, and educational stakeholders. This research is expected to enrich the understanding of factors influencing teacher performance in madrasah aliyah and educational leadership in Islamic education more broadly. In Sukmadinata's perspective (Sukmadinata 2019), the reasons for choosing this research problem and title meet two elements: (1) the problem is of interest and aligns with the researcher's discipline, with supporting literature available; and (2) the problem is essential, urgent, and beneficial to solve, valuable as the experience of madrasah aliyah heads and teachers that is useful for others, original as it proves something new that is essential, and practical as a lesson learned for other madrasah aliyah heads and teachers.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research employs a qualitative approach with a descriptive-analytical method to thoroughly describe and analyze the leadership strategies of madrasah heads in improving teachers' performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangkaraya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, Central Kalimantan, Indonesia. Data was collected through documentation studies, interviews, and observations, and analyzed using the Miles and Huberman model (Mezmir 2020), which involves four stages. Additionally, a literature review technique was utilized (Kosasih and Al Mighwar 2024).

The stages are: (1) data collection, conducted through documentation studies, including primary sources such as Madrasah Aliyah's Work Plans (RKM), Annual Work Plans (RKT), Income and Expenditure Budget Plans, Activity Plans, Budgets, Head Performance Reports, Teacher Performance Reports, and secondary sources like academic journals, books, and research papers on Kotten's leadership strategy, Richard and Steers' performance, Maslow's performance motivation, and the concept of teacher performance in Permendiknas 16/2007 and PMA 38/2018, as well as the Indonesian government's policy regarding the performance of heads and teachers of madrasah aliyah; interviews with key informants at MA Muslimat NU Palangkaraya (Mashudi as Head, Fahzur Kasihani and Rusmini as deputies, Salasiah and Zulfikar Hamzah as teachers, Ananda Yudha Prasetyo, Ghina Ulfah, and Risma Oktviani as students) and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau (Muliani as Head, Salbiah and Nur Hayati as deputies, Syarbaini and Irfansyah as teachers, Achmad Akbar, Ahmad Fahmi, and Aditia Pratama as students); and observations through field visits and moderate participation in various teacher competency development activities at MA Muslimat NU Palangkaraya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau over approximately six months (May-October 2023); (2) data reduction, where the collected data is condensed, categorized, and distilled to highlight the most crucial information and identify themes and patterns; (3) data display, where the reduced data is organized and presented in a coherent narrative, often supplemented by graphics or charts; and (4) conclusion drawing/verifying, where the presented data is interpreted, validated, and conclusions are drawn to address the research objectives.

Figure 1: Miles and Huberman Model Data Analysis Process

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on data collected through triangulation methods, including documentation reviews, interviews, and field observations of both primary and secondary sources, as well as comprehensive data analysis at MA Muslimat NU Palangkaraya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, the following results and discussions are presented:

1. Madrasah Management Strategy (Corporate Strategy) of the Principal in Improving Teacher Performance

The Corporate Strategy implemented by principals at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau includes: emphasizing Islamic values, quality education, and student character development; setting specific goals to improve learning quality and academic achievements through annual work plans and teacher development; instilling core values like honesty, discipline, responsibility, and justice into organizational culture and daily practices; and initiating continuous training programs, developing learning facilities, and implementing competency-oriented curriculum for teachers.

This highlights the principals' robust approach to foundational strategies. The Corporate Strategy implemented by the principals of MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau integrates Pancasila's philosophical, theological, logical, and ethical principles. Mission statements emphasize Islamic values and quality education, guided by QS. Al-Anbiyaa: 73, highlighting leaders' roles in fostering goodness and holistic development as envisioned in Pancasila. This approach aligns with Kotten's corporate strategy theory, emphasizing a clear mission as foundational to organizational goals. Policies like PMA 58/2017 jo. PMA 24/2018 underscore the importance of mission clarity in evaluating principal performance. Specific, measurable goals at both madrasahs are rooted in philosophical, theological, logical, and ethical principles essential for achieving goodness and aligning with religious teachings and Pancasila's human development ideals. Kotten's theory on goal formulation supports the role of clear objectives in guiding organizational activities, reinforced by policies in principal performance evaluation under PMA 58/2017 jo. PMA 24/2018. Institutional values are shaped by Pancasila's philosophical tenets and QS. Al-Anbiyaa: 73's theological teachings, promote moral integrity within the organizational culture. Kotten's theory on value formulation in corporate strategy strengthens this culture, supported by policies assessing principal performance and emphasizing values' role in madrasah development. Strategic initiatives at both madrasahs, grounded in Pancasila, aim to enhance educational quality and teacher performance, emphasizing initiative formulation's pivotal role in achieving organizational objectives, aligned with policies such as PMA 58/2017 jo. PMA 24/2018. Overall, the principals' corporate strategy at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau integrates Pancasila's philosophical foundation, theological insights, logical reasoning, and ethical principles with Kotten's theory and relevant policies, aiming to enhance educational quality and teacher performance in madrasahs while adhering to moral teachings, religious principles, the Sanusi value system, management theories, and educational policies. This alignment is supported by research, such as Hakim's study on principal planning's impact on teachers' professional competence at MIN 04 Kepahiang.

2. Madrasah Program Strategy (Program Strategy) of the Principal in Improving Teacher Performance

The research findings indicate that the Madrasah Program Strategy implemented by the principals at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau includes monitoring the strategic implications of programs such as technology training to enhance teaching quality and teacher performance, responsiveness to program evaluations through adjustments or the development of more effective new programs, and involving teachers in discussions and strategic program planning to ensure relevance to the needs and challenges of the teaching staff.

In this discussion, the Madrasah Program Strategy employed by the principals to enhance teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau reflects a robust approach to several pertinent foundations. The Madrasah Program Strategy employed by principals at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau to enhance teacher performance reflects a comprehensive approach rooted in several foundational aspects. Research indicates that this strategy involves monitoring the strategic implications of initiatives such as technology training to improve teaching quality and teacher performance, adapting programs based on evaluations to ensure effectiveness, and engaging teachers in strategic planning to address their specific needs and challenges. Aligned with Pancasila's philosophy, which emphasizes holistic human development, including education, this strategy also resonates with theological teachings, exemplified by QS. Al-Anbiyaa: 73 and HR. Muslim, stressing the leader's role in guiding virtuous actions. Principals' attention to strategic implications underscores their spiritual and moral responsibilities as educational leaders in the madrasah context. Emphasizing program evaluation as integral to effective leadership strategies, in line with Kotten's theory, ensures the successful implementation of these strategies. Policies like PMA 58/2017 and PMA 24/2018 underscore the importance of program evaluation and monitoring in assessing principal performance and enhancing educational quality in madrasahs, reflecting teleological principles within the Sanusi value system aimed at achieving ultimate societal good through effective leadership.

3. Madrasah Resource Support Strategy (Resource Support Strategy) of the Principal in Improving Teacher Performance

The research findings indicate that the resource support strategy employed by school principals to enhance teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangkaraya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau includes leveraging human resources, financial resources, infrastructure, and technology.

This strategy illustrates a robust approach to several pertinent foundations. The strategies employed at MA Muslimat NU Palangkaraya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau in utilizing human, financial, infrastructure, and technological resources align with Pancasila's principles of social justice and improving citizens' quality of life, including teachers. These strategies encompass providing spiritual guidance and continuous professional development for teachers, reinforcing Kotten's resource support strategy theory. Policies such as PMA 58/2017 jo. PMA 24/2018 emphasize enhancing principal performance in HR management, in line with educational policies like Permendiknas 16/2007 and PMA 38/2018 that stress the importance of teacher

professional development. Efficient financial management reflects Pancasila's values of justice and humanity, supporting institutional strategies and enhancing organizational performance. The effective use of facilities and infrastructure supports educational goals, highlighting the need for adequate educational resources as per PMA 58/2017 jo. PMA 24/2018, consistent with research indicating infrastructure planning can enhance teacher competence. Technology integration in education supports national development goals, imbued with ethical values, and enhances teaching effectiveness, aligning with policies and research supporting technology's role in teacher professionalism. These efforts underscore the comprehensive alignment with philosophical, theological, leadership theory, and educational policy foundations, effectively enhancing teacher performance.

4. Madrasah Strategy (Institutional Strategy) of the Principal in Improving Teacher Performance

The research findings indicate that institutional strategies employed by school principals to enhance teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau include developing organizational capabilities, drafting annual and long-term work plans, utilizing a clear authority structure, and aligning madrasah strategies with national education policies and community needs through active participation and external collaboration.

This discussion highlights that the institutional strategies implemented by school principals to improve teacher performance reflect a robust approach to several relevant foundations. The institutional strategies implemented by school principals at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau to enhance teacher performance encompass several key elements. These include developing organizational capabilities in line with Pancasila's ethos of fostering collective ability to achieve high educational goals and aligning with ethical values espoused by Sanusi. This approach emphasizes organizational capacity development as a strategy for optimizing resources and achieving strategic objectives, consistent with Kotten's recourse support strategy theory. Additionally, the utilization of clear authority structures in both madrasahs reflects principles of fairness in Pancasila and Islamic teachings on guiding those under authority, as articulated in QS. Al-Anbiyaa: 73. Effective organizational structure utilization to attain madrasah's strategic goals is underscored, alongside compliance with PMA 58/2017 and PMA 24/2018 policies. The relevance of Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) ensures operational efficiency, reflecting principles of justice and efficiency in Pancasila and QS. Al-Anbiyaa: 73, crucial for maintaining consistency in organizational operations aligned with Kotten's theory. This comprehensive approach supports principal performance assessment and managerial task implementation, crucial for educational development, as indicated by Rinaldi's research on enhancing professionalism at MA plus Walisongo, Lampung Utara. Thus, it can be concluded that these resource support strategies adopted by principals align with the philosophical foundations of Pancasila, Sanusi's value system, Kotten's recourse support strategy theory, and relevant policy concepts (PMA 58/2017 and PMA 24/2018), contributing significantly to improving madrasah teacher performance, bolstered by pertinent prior research findings.

5. Obstacles Faced by the Principal in Improving Teacher Performance

Research findings indicate that the obstacles faced by the principals of MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau are similar, encompassing common barriers such as insufficient human resource alignment, inadequate infrastructure, and budget limitations. Moreover, specific challenges include difficulty adapting to educational and technological changes, managing conflicts, limited engagement, and communication skills, as well as inadequate capability in applying situational leadership.

In this discussion, the barriers encountered by school principals in enhancing teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau reflect a robust approach to several pertinent foundations. The challenges faced by principals at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau encompass both general and specific barriers. General obstacles include inadequate human resource alignment, affecting teaching effectiveness and management, with principles of fairness and balance highlighted in Pancasila philosophy and Islamic values. The lack of infrastructure similarly impacts learning processes and teacher performance, requiring strategic leadership to manage these resources effectively. Budget constraints further restrict teacher performance and essential program implementation, demanding prudent financial management. Specific challenges like adaptation to educational changes, conflict management, engagement and communication skills, and situational leadership deficiencies hinder operational efficiency. Addressing these challenges involves government policies supporting HR development, infrastructure improvement, and leadership training aligned with Pancasila and Sanusi values, crucial for enhancing teacher performance in madrasah education.

6. Solutions to Overcome the Obstacles Faced by the Principal in Improving Teacher Performance

The research results indicate that the Head of MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and the Head of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau employ two main strategies to address general and specific challenges: consolidation (resource management efficiency, financial management improvement, and securing additional funding) and expansion (networking and increasing revenue through partnerships and paid educational services). The implementation of these strategies is expected to overcome obstacles related to human resources, facilities, and budgets, as well as enhance teacher performance and overall education quality. In this discussion, the solutions implemented by the headmasters to overcome obstacles in improving teacher performance at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau demonstrate a strong approach to several relevant foundations. The headmasters at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau adopt consolidation and expansion strategies to address general and specific obstacles. Consolidation strategies ensure efficient resource management, and financial management improvements, and seek additional funding, reflecting Pancasila's social justice values and Sanusi's emphasis on logical and ethical resource allocation. Supported by Humphrey's SWOT analysis, these strategies align with safety needs in Maslow's theory and Richard and Steers' performance and adjustment theories, and comply with Kepdirjenpendis Kemenag RI regulations. Expansion strategies focus on extending partnerships and income

sources, aligning with Pancasila's democracy and national development values and Sanusi's teleological aspects. This approach addresses social and esteem needs in Maslow's theory and enhances job satisfaction, supported by Nuraida's research on teacher professionalism. To address specific obstacles like adaptability, conflict management, engagement, communication, and situational leadership, solutions emphasize Pancasila's unity values, Sanusi's logical and ethical aspects, and comply with educational policies. These solutions meet self-actualization, social, and esteem needs in Maslow's theory and enhance professional competence, supported by various studies. In conclusion, the proposed solutions by the headmasters effectively reflect religious, philosophical, theoretical, policy, and value system foundations, demonstrating a strong commitment to improving educational quality and performance in the madrasahs.

7. Performance Results of Teachers

The research results indicate that the teacher performance assessment at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya shows an average score of 86.7 (Good), with the average performance score of the madrasah principal being 86.06 (Good). On the other hand, the teacher performance assessment at MAN 1 Pulang Pisau shows an average score of 86.2 (Good), with the average performance score of the madrasah principal being 90.36 (Very Good). These findings provide a holistic view that most teachers in both madrasahs have met or even exceeded the required competency standards, although there is a slight difference in the average performance scores. In this discussion, the teacher performance results at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau reflect a strong approach to several relevant foundations.

In this discussion, the teacher performance results at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau illustrate a strong approach to several relevant foundations. Teachers at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau meet or exceed competence standards in pedagogical, personality, social, and professional areas. They exhibit strong pedagogical skills by designing lessons to meet students' needs, using diverse methods, and effectively evaluating outcomes, aligning with Pancasila, Sanusi's Value System, and educational policies (Permendiknas 16/2007 and PMA 38/2018). They demonstrate positive attitudes, empathy, and good relationships, fostering a harmonious environment consistent with Pancasila and relevant policies (UU 14/2005, PP 74/2008). They effectively interact with students, colleagues, and parents, promoting inclusivity and social justice, as supported by Nuraida's research and Q.S. at-Taubah: 105. Additionally, they meet professional standards and engage in self-development, reflecting the values of Pancasila and the emphasis on quality in Sanusi's Value System, supported by policies (Kepdirjenpendis 5581/2021) and research by Ikbal and HR. Muslim. Their performance aligns with these foundations, emphasizing objective assessment and tangible results. Based on these findings and discussions, the researcher developed a novel research product aimed at continuously improving the quality of Madrasah Aliyah teacher performance through the leadership strategies of Madrasah heads. This product, titled 'Hypothetical Model for Sustainable Improvement of Madrasah Aliyah Teacher Performance through Leadership Strategies of Madrasah Heads,' is shown in the following figure.

Figure 2: 'Hypothetical Model for Sustainable Improvement of Madrasah Aliyah Teacher Performance through Leadership Strategies of Madrasah Heads.'

The chart visualizes that the optimization of Madrasah Aliyah teacher performance through the leadership strategies of madrasah heads can be achieved through five continuous steps or stages:

- SWOT Analysis of Continuous Needs for Madrasah Aliyah Teachers:** This step involves Humphrey's SWOT Analysis of the needs of Madrasah Aliyah teachers, aligned with the teacher performance concept in Permendiknas 16/2007, to produce recommendations for either expansion or consolidation, aimed at sustainable teacher performance optimization.
- Foundation:** This step involves grounding in the philosophy of Pancasila, Sanusi's value system, Kotten's leadership strategy theory, policies PMA 58/2017 and PMA 38/2018, and current research, which form the basis for formulating and implementing leadership strategies.
- Leadership Strategy of Madrasah Aliyah Heads:** This step involves implementing Kotten's leadership strategy model, aligned with PMA 58/2017, which consists of four sub-strategies: (1) Corporate Strategy: Focusing on formulating the mission, objectives, values, and strategic initiatives; (2) Program Strategy: Focusing on the strategic program implications for madrasah development; (3) Resource Support Strategy: Focusing on maximizing the use of essential resources like workforce, finance, technology, etc.; and (4) Institutional Strategy: Focusing on developing organizational capabilities to execute strategic initiatives.
- Optimization of Madrasah Aliyah Teacher Performance Priorities:** This step involves prioritizing the optimization of Madrasah Aliyah teacher performance based on the previous

- SWOT analysis and guided by PMA 38/2018, which includes four main competencies: (1) Pedagogic: Mastery of learning theories, curriculum development, educational teaching practices, student potential development, communication, and assessment and evaluation; (2) Personality: Acting by religious, legal, social, and national cultural norms, demonstrating maturity, role-model behavior, work ethic, responsibility, and pride as a teacher; (3) Professional: Mastery of material, scientific concepts, and professional development through reflection; and (4) Social: Being inclusive, objective, non-discriminatory, and able to communicate with other teachers, educational staff, students' parents, and the community.
- e. Excellent Performance of Madrasah Aliyah Teachers: The ultimate goal of this cycle is to achieve excellent performance of Madrasah Aliyah teachers through effective leadership strategies and teacher performance optimization.

Each element in this model supports and sustains the others, creating a cycle that continuously improves and optimizes the performance of Madrasah Aliyah teachers

CONCLUSION

Based on previous research, it is concluded that the leadership strategies of the heads of madrasahs at MA Muslimat NU Palangka Raya and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau align with Kotten's leadership strategies, Richard and Steers' performance theories, and Maslow's motivation theory. These strategies, grounded in Pancasila, Sanusi's value system, and the theological values of the Quran and Hadith, have enhanced teacher performance.

Specifically, first, Management Strategy: Principals have formulated mission, goals, values, and initiatives to enhance teacher performance, aligning with Kotten's corporate strategy. Second, Program Strategy: Principals have clear strategies for madrasah programs, considering strategic implications for teacher performance. Third, Resource Support Strategy: Principals maximize essential resources (human, financial, and technological) to improve teacher performance. Fourth, Organizational Development: Principals develop organizational capabilities to implement strategic initiatives that support teacher performance improvement. Fifth, Obstacle Management: Principals address general and specific obstacles with appropriate strategies to avoid hindering teacher performance. Sixth, Overcoming Obstacles: Principals use consolidation and expansion strategies to overcome obstacles and improve teacher performance. Seventh, Performance Improvement: Teacher performance has shown improvement in pedagogical competence, personality, social competence, and professionalism, aligning with theories from Richard and Steers, Maslow, Permendiknas 16/2007, and PMA 38/2018.

To improve the performance of Madrasah Aliyah teachers, the principal should apply effective leadership and provide support and training, teachers should be involved in professional development and innovative teaching, students should provide feedback and participate actively, and researchers should study leadership and performance factors. The researchers' findings and research product offerings can be used as material for consideration for implementation.

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